

Ethnobotanical Assessment of Medicinal Plants Used in Brass, Nembe and Ogbia Local Government Areas of Bayelsa State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study aimed to document and evaluate the diversity, uses, and sources of medicinal plants utilized by indigenous communities in Eastern Bayelsa State, Nigeria. The study was conducted across three Local Government Areas Brass, Nembe, and Ogbia located within the Niger Delta region. Data was collected from a total of 89 respondents, comprising traditional healers, herbal medicine vendors, and elderly individuals, through structured questionnaires and oral interviews. The survey identified a total of 54 medicinal plant species belonging to 28 botanical families, which are commonly used for the treatment and management of various ailments. Data collection focused on plant identification, local names, plant parts used, preparation methods, and therapeutic applications. The findings revealed that most medicinal plants are sourced from uncultivated lands, communal forests, protected areas, and farmlands. Leaves and stem bark were the most frequently utilized plant parts, while preparation methods commonly involved decoction, maceration, and infusion using water, palm wine, or local gin. The results further indicated a strong reliance on traditional medicine among inhabitants, largely due to its accessibility, affordability, and perceived effectiveness despite increasing availability of synthetic drugs. In conclusion, the study highlights the rich ethnomedicinal knowledge and plant diversity in Eastern Bayelsa State, emphasizing the need for conservation of these plant resources and scientific validation of their pharmacological properties for sustainable healthcare development.

Keywords: Weeds, Medicinal plants, Ethnobotany, Plant diversity.

Introduction

Throughout the ages, mankind has relied on the natural world (especially plants) for their basic needs such as treatments of diseases, housings, edible materials, perfumes, apparel, relishes, manures and means of conveyance over the years. Medicinal plants continue to play a critical role in primary healthcare systems globally, especially in developing regions where access to orthodox medicine is often limited due to cost, availability, and infrastructural constraints (World Health Organization, 2019; Petrovska, 2016). In sub-Saharan Africa, including Nigeria, traditional herbal medicine remains an integral component of healthcare delivery, with a significant proportion of the population depending on plant-based remedies for disease management. Medicinal plants derive their therapeutic efficacy from biologically active compounds known as phytochemicals, which exhibit pharmacological properties such as antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and anticancer activities (Ekor, 2014; Yuan *et al.*, 2016). These bioactive constituents have contributed immensely to modern drug discovery, with several conventional pharmaceuticals originating directly or indirectly from plant sources.

Despite advances in synthetic drug development, medicinal plants remain indispensable due to their relative affordability, cultural acceptance, and perceived safety. However, indigenous knowledge associated with medicinal plants is increasingly under threat, particularly in regions such as Bayelsa State in the Niger Delta. Rapid urbanization, environmental degradation from oil exploration, loss of biodiversity, and the gradual erosion of traditional belief systems have significantly contributed to the decline in ethnobotanical knowledge (Chinsebu, 2016; Ozioma & Chinwe, 2019). Additionally, the oral mode of knowledge transmission typically from older generations to younger ones is weakening due to modernization, formal education systems, and reduced interest among youths in traditional practices. The ecological challenges in Bayelsa State further exacerbate this situation. Oil pollution, habitat destruction, and poor environmental sanitation have not only reduced the availability of medicinal plant species but have also altered their phytochemical composition, potentially affecting their therapeutic efficacy (UNEP, 2018; Aghalino & Eyinla, 2020). Concurrently, increasing disease burden linked to polluted water sources and poor living conditions has intensified reliance on herbal medicine, particularly among low-income populations who may lack access to conventional healthcare services.

Notwithstanding the continued dependence on medicinal plants, there is a significant knowledge gap regarding the systematic documentation, preservation, and scientific validation of indigenous medicinal plant use in eastern Bayelsa State. Much of the existing knowledge remains fragmented, undocumented, and at risk of permanent loss as elder custodians pass away without transferring their expertise. Furthermore, there is limited contemporary research that integrates ethnobotanical data with current environmental and socio-economic realities in the region. Therefore, this study seeks to address this gap by systematically documenting medicinal plant species used in eastern Bayelsa State, including the plant parts utilized, methods of preparation, and the categories of ailments treated. By creating a comprehensive and up-to-date database, this research contributes to the preservation of indigenous knowledge, supports future pharmacological investigations, and provides a foundation for integrating traditional medicine into sustainable healthcare systems.

Materials and Methods

Study area

Bayelsa State is a coastal state in South-South Nigeria, located in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria. The state was created in October 1996, being carved out from Rivers State during the then military regime of late Gen. Sani Abacha, strategically locating Yenagoa as its administrative capital. With an estimated population of 2,537,400 (4,159 sq. mi) in 2022, the state occupies 10,773 square kilometres. It shares boundary with Rivers State to the east and Delta State to the across the Niger River for 17 km and the Forcados River for 198 km, with the waters of the Atlantic Ocean. The study was carried out in Eastern Bayelsa state encompassing three Local Government Areas (Brass, Nembe and Ogbia). Having an equatorial climate type, the study area experiences rainfall almost every month of the year with a mean monthly temperature of 25° C to 31° C (Digitemie *et al.*, 2022). The study area frequently experiences harsh heat and waterlessness from December to March, with a relative humidity that is high all through the year and declines steadily in the dry season. The source of revenue for dwellers in the study area is subsistence agriculture, mainly cultivation of crops such as cassava, water yam, sweet potato, cocoyam, palm oil production and fishing activities.

Sampling Technique

The study employed a purposive sampling technique, whereby respondents were selected based on their knowledge and involvement in traditional medicine. A total of 89 respondents, comprising traditional healers, herbal medicine sellers, and elderly individuals, were deliberately chosen due to their expertise in medicinal plant use. This method was appropriate as it ensured the inclusion of key informants with relevant ethnobotanical knowledge.

Data Analysis

Data collected were analysed using both quantitative and qualitative approaches. Quantitative data was subjected to descriptive statistics, including frequencies and percentages, and presented in tables. Qualitative data obtained from oral interviews were analysed using thematic analysis, where responses were categorized into themes such as plant uses, preparation methods, and sources. This combined approach enabled a comprehensive interpretation of medicinal plant utilization in the study area.

Results

Results (Table 1) represent a total of 54 plant species belonging to 28 families established as commonly used therapeutic plants in the study area. These remedies were identified by traditional healers and herbal medicine vendors as being commonly used in the management and treatment of various health conditions. Detailed information on the plant species, including their botanical names, taxonomic families, therapeutic uses, specific plant parts utilized, as well as methods of preparation and administration is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Some medicinal plants useful in Eastern Bayelsa, their uses, preparation and administration

S/N	Common name	Botanical name	Family	Part of plant used	Disease cured	Preparation and administration
1	Mountain thistle	<i>Acanthus montanus</i>	Acanthaceae	Roots and leaves	Gonorrhoea, wounds, syphilis, cough.	Freshly collected roots are washed clean with water, mashed and added to locally brewed alcohol (Gin). The extract is taken 20mls twice daily. Ground leaves are placed over heat and put on wound daily till wound heals.
2	Cashew	<i>Anacardium occidentale</i>	Anacardiaceae	Tree bark	Whooping cough	Tree bark is collected and ground to pulp. This is extracted with clean water. Extract is taken 20mls, 2 times daily.
3	Sour sop	<i>Anona muricata</i>	Annonaceae	Root stem bark leaves	Venereal diseases Intestinal ailments mouth odour, tooth ache, sores	The root decoction with native natron is taken with pepper for about 6 days. Pulverized root and dried leaves extract is applied directly to sores. Stem bark infusion is chewed for mouth odour and tooth ache.
4	Goat weed	<i>Ageratum conyzoides</i>	Asteraceae	Leaves and stem	Fever, genital warts, gonorrhoea	Fresh leaves and stem are ground and the sap squeezed out to rub on genital warts or used as enema for fever and gonorrhoea.
5	Candle bush	<i>Senna alata</i>	Fabaceae	Leaves	Skin diseases such as ringworm, eczema and scabies	Extracts obtained from young leaves are scrubbed on infected part of the skin
6	Guava	<i>Psidium guajava</i>	Myrtaceae	Leaves	Laxative, Malaria, Diarrhoea	Leaves are boiled and extract taken orally. It can also be taken fresh for fast action in the case of Laxative
7	Moringa plant	<i>Moringa oleifera</i>	Moringaceae	Flower, leaves, stem, bark and roots	Cough asthma Liver, pancreas and scurvy ailments	Flower, leaves, stem bark and roots are washed, chopped, dried and sprinkled on food as required by individual.
8	Lime	<i>Citrus aurantifolia</i>	Rutaceae	Fruits and roots	Gonorrhoea, malaria, jaundice, deworming.	12 ampicillin capsules are added to 600mls of lime juice and 20mls of concoction's taken twice daily. Root is extracted with palm wine or local gin and taken orally.
9	Black plum	<i>Vitex doniana</i>	Verbanaceae	Stem	Tooth decay	Stem is sliced into short thin pieces and chewed

10	Garden egg	<i>Solanum melongera</i>	Solanaceae	Leaves and roots	Rheumatism Swollen joints Rashes	Poultice of the leaves and roots are pound with local white chalk and applied on the affected area.
11	African star apple	<i>Chrysophyllum albidum</i>	Sapotaceae	Stem bark	Fever, cold, stomach pains	Decoction of the stem bark is dissolved in local gin and taken orally.
12	Bitter leaf	<i>Vernonia amygdalina</i>	Asteraceae	Leaf Roots stem twigs	Pneumonia Diabetes Astringent Stomach problems	Extracts of all part is taken orally. Roots and stem twigs are chewed.
13	Kinkéliba	<i>Combretum micranthum</i>	Combretaceae	Roots	Prolonged labour	Roots are boiled in water and extract taken orally
14	Bush sugarcane	<i>Costus afar</i>	Zingiberaceae	Leaves and stem	Eczema ringworm malaria cholera measles	Crude aqueous extracts of ground leaves are rubbed on affected lesion and are also taken as enema. Stem extract mixed with native chalk is rubbed on skin for measles.
15	Mango	<i>Mangifera indica</i>	Anacardiaceae	Tree bark	Malaria jaundice fever, pains	Stem bark is cut into pieces, boiled and taken orally. Usually, a concoction with <i>Salacia pyriformis</i> is taken orally
16	Black afara	<i>Terminalia ivorensis</i>	Combretaceae	Bark	Arthritis Piles Constipation Stomach ache	The bark is ground into powder and its red decoction taken orally
17	Haemorrhage plant or wild sunflower	<i>Aspila africana</i>	Asteraceae	Leaf root	Wounds internal bleeding stomach ache lumbago	The fresh leaves is squeezed and applied to wounds. Women with internal bleeding sit on hot decoction of the leaves.
18	Bitter apple	<i>Colocynthis vulgaris</i>	Cucurbitaceae	Fruit pulp	Cathartic	Extract of boiled fruit pulp taken orally.
19	African false currant	<i>Manniophyton africanum</i>	Euphorbiaceae	Leaves	Snake bite	Leaves are macerated and rubbed on the affected area.
20	Ethiopian pepper	<i>Xylopia aethiopica</i>	Annonaceae	Fruits Bark	Cough, Analgesic	Fruits of mature plant are fried into a porous black solid. Ground and mixed with little palm oil. 2 tablespoonful to be taken by adults while children take one
21	Asthma weed	<i>Euphorbia hirta</i>	Euphorbiaceae	Shoot	Asthma, skin diseases	Plant extract in water taken orally. Extract of plant squeezed onto infected areas.
22	Christmas bush	<i>Alchornea cordifolia</i>	Euphorbiaceae	Leaves bark root fruit	Cold rheumatic pains urethral disease purgative	Leaves are macerated or chewed with other herbs such as <i>Myrianthus arboreus</i> .

					dysentery gonorrhoea	
23	Scent leaf	<i>Ocimum gratissimum</i>	Labiatae	Leaves root	Cough Cold catarrh chest pains, colic diarrhoea, pile	Leaves are inhaled while hot, plug the nostrils for five minutes with squeezed leaf paste. The roots are chewed.
24	Sweet basil	<i>Ocimum basilicum</i>	Labiatae	Whole plant leaf seeds	Headache Cough Cold Gonorrhoea Constipation Dysentery	Decoction of the whole plant is taken orally.
25	Thorn mimosa	<i>Acacia nilotica</i>	Fabaceae	Leaves root bark seeds	Astringent chest pains pneumonia dysentery diarrhoea haemorrhoids	Extracts of leaves, root, stem bark and seeds are extracted using gin and taken orally.
26	Bitter cola	<i>Garcinia kola</i>	Gutiferae	Fruits roots	Gonorrhoea, cough, tooth decay	Fruit is eaten for cough. Roots are soaked in local gin and drunk and also used to gaggle.
27	Ogbonno	<i>Irvingia gabonensis</i>	Irvingiaceae	Stem bark	Spleen infection	The decoction of stem and bark is mixed with that of <i>Aspilia Africana</i> and taken orally.
28	Upland cotton	<i>Gossypum hirsutum</i>	Malvaceae	Leaves	Measles, small pox	Leaves are ground into a pulp. This is mixed with clay and water to form a paste.
29	Ginger	<i>Zingiber officinale</i>	Zingiberaceae	Rhizome	Cough	Rhizome are ground and extracted with hot water and taken as tea or chewed
30	Sweet orange	<i>Citrus sinensis</i>	Rutaceae	Leaves Roots	Malaria fever Diarrhoea	Leaves are soaked in palm wine or boiled with water and filtrate taken orally.
31	Bamboo	<i>Bambusa vulgaris</i>	Poaceae	Leaf shoot	Abortifacient Vomiting of blood wounds respiratory diseases gonorrhoea	The leaves decoction is taken orally for abortion. The leaf juice is given for vomiting of blood. Young shoot poultice is applied directly to wounds while its decoction is taken for respiratory diseases. The young shoot extracted with local gin together with tobacco leaves and native salt is taken two shots twice daily for gonorrhoea.
32	Wire grass	<i>Eleusine indica</i>	Poaceae	Roots	Cough	Roots of mature grass are soaked and extracted with warm water and taken orally for cough.
33	Garlic	<i>Allium sativum</i>	Amaryllidaceae	Bulbs	Cough, skin disease, hypertension, diabetes	Bulb is eaten for cough. Bulbs are soaked in local gin for at least 12hrs before drinking, bulbs are

						ground and used to cure skin diseases.
34	Onion	<i>Allium cepa</i>	Amaryllidaceae	Bulbs	Cough, eye pains, hypertension, diabetes	Bulb is eaten for cough and eye pains. Bulbs are soaked in local gin for at least 12hrs before drinking. Skin diseases.
35	Wire weed	<i>Sida acuta</i>	Malvaceae	Whole plant	Kidney, blood and liver infections	Decoction of whole plant is used to treat ailment and can be taken orally when warm
36	Lemon grass	<i>Cymbopogon citratus</i>	Poaceae	Leaves	Fevers, catarrh, cough and kidney diseases	Fresh leaves are collected, washed with clean water and boiled. The decoction is taken orally for cough, fever, kidney diseases and inhaled when hot to relief catarrh
37	Water leaf	<i>Talinum triangulare</i>		Whole plant	Anaemia, cancer, liver and heart diseases	Succulent leaves of plant are crumpled in 2 litres of drinkable water. Half glass to be taken before meal 2 times daily.
38	Pig weed	<i>Amaranthus spinosus</i>	Amaranthaceae	Whole plant	Jaundice, ulcer, dysentery and kidney diseases	Decoction of whole plant is used to treat ailment and can be taken orally when warm
39	Green amaranth	<i>Amaranthus viridis</i>	Amaranthaceae	Whole plant	Stomach aches, inflammation, boils, kidney diseases and gonorrhoea	Decoction of whole plant is used to treat ailment and can be taken orally when warm
40	Fluted pumpkin	<i>Telferia occidentalis</i>	Curcubitaceae	Leaves	Anaemia, blood infection	Treat Anaemia by squeezing the leaves, drinking the extract with a mixture of malt drink twice daily and children half the dosage.
41	Pepper	<i>Capsicum annum</i>	Solanaceae	Seed and fruit	Wound, broken bones	Fruits and seeds are grounded and placed on wounds and broken bones tied with a banding material
42	Alligator pepper	<i>Aframomum melegueta</i>	Zingiberaceae	Root and seed	Sleeping sickness, wound, cough and sore throat	Seed is grounded and mixed with local gin and placed on wounds. Dry seeds are chewed raw for cough and sore throat
43	Neem plant	<i>Azadiractha indica</i>	Meliaceae	Stem, bark, leaves and roots	Malaria, boils, fever, stomach aches	The useful parts of the plant are boiled and a full glass of the filtrate is taken 3 times daily. It is also added to local gin
44	Hog plum	<i>Spondias mombin</i>	Anacardiaceae	Stem, bark, leaves and roots	Infertility	Decoction of leaves, bark, roots can be taken orally, sometimes with little local gin
45	Never die plant	<i>Bryophyllum pinnatum</i>	Crassulaceae	Leaves	Inflammatory, wounds, ear treatment, healing of	The leaves are expose to heat from fire, few drops are applied into the ear, wound (using the leave to cover the surface and

					new-born baby navel	tied) and on the surface of the navel to heal for new born babies
46	Almond tree	<i>Terminalia catappa</i>	Combretaceae	Bark, roots, leaves	Sleeplessness, Insomnia	Decoction of leaves, bark, roots mixed with Lemon grass can be taken orally
47	Siam weed	<i>Chromolaena odorata</i>	Asteraceae	Root, leaves	Malaria, fever, dysentery, healing of wound, blood clotting	Succulent leaves are squeezed and droplet of it is placed on wounds. Roots and leaves are mixed with leaves of <i>Citrus</i> and bark of <i>Mangifera indica</i> is boiled and taken orally for malaria and fever. Women use it to control internal bleeding by sitting on hot decoction of the leaves.
48	Morning glory	<i>Ipomoea involucrata</i>	Convolvulaceae	Leaves	Pneumonia	Leaves are grounded with a mixture of water. Before breakfast, take mixture with addition of half a teaspoon of salt.
49	African nutmeg	<i>Monodora myristica</i>	Annonaceae	Seeds	Diarrhoea	Depending on the degree of stooling, chew 5-10 seed to stop diarrhoea
50	Physic nut	<i>Jatropha curcas</i>	Euphorbiaceae	Leaves	Tongue disease, snake bite	Latex from the leaf should be placed on cotton wool and used to clean the tongue to remove dirt and infections on the tongue. Snake bite can be treated by drinking water obtained from the leaves
51	Hospital too far	<i>Jatropha tanjorensis</i>	Euphorbiaceae	Leaves	Malaria, Anaemia, heart disease, kidney disease	Leaves decoction and fresh succulent leaves can be squeezed and taken orally.
52	Sponge gourd	<i>Luffa cylindrical</i>	Curcubitaceae	Leaves	Boil, swollen portions	Subject mature leaves to heat in order to soften them and squeeze to obtain liquid content. Add some ashes, and then apply to a boil or swollen spot.
53	Kola	<i>Cola nitida</i>	Sterculiaceae	Root and fruits	Arthritis rheumatism	The root is soaked in local gin and taken orally. Fruit is eaten raw
54	Pawpaw	<i>Carica papaya</i>	Caricaceae	Leaves, fruits	Whitlow syphilis, malaria, mental issues, diabetes	Decoction of leaves and unripe fruit is used to cure ailments when taken orally. Latex should be applied on affected finger at least four times daily for whitlow.

S/N	Family	Frequency (%)
1	Acanthaceae	1 (1.9)
2	Amaranthaceae	2 (3.7)
3	Amaryllidaceae	2 (3.7)
4	Anacardiaceae	3 (5.5)
5	Annonaceae	3 (5.5)
6	Asteraceae	4 (7.4)
7	Caricaceae	1 (1.9)
8	Combretaceae	3 (5.5)
9	Convolvulaceae	1 (1.9)
10	Crassulaceae	1 (1.9)
11	Curcubitaceae	3 (5.5)
12	Euphorbiaceae	5 (9.3)
13	Fabaceae	2 (3.7)
14	Gutiferae	1 (1.9)
15	Irvingiaceae	1 (1.9)
16	Labiatae	2 (3.7)
17	Malvaceae	2 (3.7)
18	Meliaceae	1 (1.9)
19	Moringaceae	1 (1.9)
20	Myrtaceae	1 (1.9)
21	Poaceae	3 (5.5)
22	Portulaceae	1 (1.9)
23	Rutaceae	2 (3.7)
24	Sapotaceae	1 (1.9)
25	Solanaceae	2 (3.7)
26	Sterculiaceae	1 (1.9)
27	Verbanaceae	1 (1.9)
28	Zingiberaceae	3 (5.5)
	Total	54 (100)

Discussion

The present ethnobotanical study provides important insights into the diversity, utilisation patterns, and socio-ecological significance of medicinal plants in Eastern Bayelsa State, Nigeria. The findings are consistent with broader ethnobotanical patterns observed across tropical regions, where plant use is shaped by a dynamic interaction between ecological availability, phytochemical properties, and cultural knowledge systems (Dery & Otsyina, 2000). The dominance of certain plant families such as Fabaceae, Euphorbiaceae, Asteraceae, and Annonaceae in the study area can be interpreted through the framework of ecological apparency theory and chemical ecology (Collins, 2005). Ecological apparency theory posits that plant species that are more abundant, conspicuous, and accessible within a given ecosystem are more likely to be recognised, utilised, and incorporated into traditional pharmacopoeia (Krishnaiah et al., 2007). The Niger Delta's humid tropical environment, characterised by high rainfall, fertile alluvial soils, and dense vegetation, supports a rich assemblage of such taxa (Ekanem & Udoh, 2009). Recent ethnobotanical syntheses in Nigeria indicate that Fabaceae remains the most dominant plant family nationwide, accounting for a substantial proportion of medicinal species across diverse ecological

zones (Rafiu *et al.*, 2025). This dominance is partly attributable to the family's nitrogen-fixing capability, which enhances soil fertility and facilitates its widespread distribution across both forested and semi-disturbed landscapes (Omosun *et al.*, 2013).

Similarly, (Yetein *et al.*, 2012) established that Euphorbiaceae and Asteraceae exhibit notable ecological adaptability, enabling them to thrive in disturbed habitats, farmlands, and forest margins areas that are readily accessible to rural populations. From a phytochemical perspective, the prominence of these families is closely linked to their diverse and potent secondary metabolites (Ampitan, 2013). For instance, members of Asteraceae are known to contain sesquiterpene lactones and flavonoids with well-documented antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory properties (Kayode *et al.*, 2008). Euphorbiaceae species are rich in alkaloids, diterpenes, and tannins, while Fabaceae species are characterised by phenolic compounds and bioactive peptides. These compounds contribute to therapeutic efficacy and reinforce their repeated utilisation and cultural validation over time. Thus, the dominance of these plant families reflects a convergence of ecological availability and pharmacological effectiveness (Ampitan, 2013). Beyond ecological considerations, the observed utilisation patterns may be further explained through the lens of ethnobotanical knowledge transmission theory. Indigenous knowledge systems are typically sustained through oral tradition, apprenticeship, and intergenerational transfer, resulting in the preferential use of culturally salient plant species.

Recent studies have demonstrated that ethnobotanical practices in Nigeria are deeply embedded within cultural identity, belief systems, and subsistence strategies, with plant usage varying across ecological zones yet maintaining notable similarities (Rafiu *et al.*, 2025). The recurrent documentation of species such as *Vernonia amygdalina*, *Carica papaya*, and *Mangifera indica* across multiple regions illustrates the concept of cross-cultural consensus, whereby certain species gain prominence due to their widely acknowledged therapeutic value. In the Niger Delta context, reliance on medicinal plants is further reinforced by limited access to formal healthcare services, economic constraints, and the perceived efficacy of herbal remedies. This aligns with the utilitarian redundancy model, which posits that multiple plant species may fulfil similar therapeutic roles, thereby enhancing the resilience and adaptability of traditional healthcare systems (Yuan *et al.* 2016). The findings of this study are consistent with recent ethnobotanical surveys conducted across Nigeria, which report similar patterns in plant family dominance and utilisation. A nationwide analysis of ethnobotanical studies documented a high diversity of medicinal plant species across numerous families, with Fabaceae, Asteraceae, and Euphorbiaceae consistently ranking among the most reported (Rafiu *et al.*, 2025). Similarly, studies conducted in Lagos State Borno State and Plateau State (Igoli *et al.*, 2003), have reported: A high representation of Fabaceae and Malvaceae in southern Nigeria, the prominence of Combretaceae and Fabaceae in savannah regions, reflecting adaptation to relatively drier conditions, a consistent preference for plant parts such as leaves and bark, owing to their availability and high concentration of bioactive compounds. The findings of this study further underscore the critical role of medicinal plants in primary healthcare delivery, particularly in rural communities (Ekor, M. 2014).

Ethnobotanical evidence indicates that plant-based remedies are widely utilised in the management of diseases such as malaria, respiratory infections, and gastrointestinal disorders, which remain prevalent in Nigeria (Lawal *et al.*, 2022; Rafiu *et al.*, 2025). From a public health perspective, this reliance reflects: the affordability and accessibility of herbal medicine, cultural acceptance and trust in traditional healing systems, limited availability of modern healthcare

infrastructure (Igoli *et al.*, 2019). Moreover, medicinal plants represent a valuable resource for pharmacological research and drug development. Numerous contemporary pharmaceuticals have been derived from plant-based compounds, and ethnobotanical knowledge provides a critical foundation for bioprospecting and therapeutic innovation. However, the integration of traditional medicine into formal healthcare systems necessitates: Rigorous phytochemical and pharmacological validation, standardization of dosage and preparation methods, comprehensive toxicological evaluation to ensure safety, development of policy frameworks to regulate traditional medicine practices. Such integration is consistent with global health strategies advocating for the inclusion of validated traditional medicine within national healthcare systems.

Conclusion

The present investigation identified 54 medicinal plant species distributed among 28 botanical families, reflecting the depth and persistence of ethnomedicinal practices in Eastern Bayelsa State. The sustained reliance on these plant resources is closely linked to their wide availability, low cost, and the confidence of users in their therapeutic value, with leaves and stem bark emerging as the most frequently exploited plant parts. Remedies are commonly prepared through decoction, maceration, infusion, and alcohol-based extraction, and are largely sourced from communal forests, farmlands, and other unmanaged landscapes. Such dependence on wild and semi-wild plant populations raises concerns about the long-term sustainability of these resources. Consequently, targeted conservation efforts, alongside rigorous phytochemical and pharmacological evaluations, are essential to validate traditional claims and facilitate the responsible incorporation of proven herbal therapies into contemporary healthcare systems.

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